

ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF THE ARAL SEA REGION AND THE PSYCHOLOGY OF THE POPULATION

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Abstract. *The creation of the Aral Sea, once the fourth largest lake in the world, is one of the world's greatest environmental tragedies. As a result of the drying up of the Aral Sea, a number of negative situations have arisen, including particles of toxic salt piles that have appeared in the Aral region, more than 75 million tons of dust and toxic salts rise from the Aral Sea every year, insufficient drinking water, the spread of dangerous diseases, and worsening living conditions. It is natural that the increasing population migration from the island region will cause social and psychological problems. The current environmental stress is self-evident. We can see a negative impact on the mental development of people living in the Aral Bay region, that is, a change in attention to the necessary objects of nature, a sharp aggressiveness in the behavior of the person. Relationships with the nature of the environment related to these existing ecological problems were studied and their comparative analysis was presented. The psychological satisfaction of the population with the way of living, the cognitive and aesthetic attitudes towards the nature of the environment for the population affected by the environmental stress were determined to be very low. It was explained that there are psychological problems in the perception of nature among the population, which have a negative effect on their personality. It takes a strong will power in a person to fight and live with the current environmental problems. A person can find the will to live in difficult ecological conditions, but the fact that he reacts with high level of aggressiveness to some of the qualities that are manifested in his personal characteristics should make any psychologists think.*

Keywords: *population psychology in the Aral Bay (Islandside) region, environmental problems and human psychology, environmental behavior, environmental consciousness.*

Introduction. In this article we opened a number of problems related to environmental problems of a global nature in the Aral Bay region, lack of drinking water for the population, shortage of irrigation water for agriculture, as a result of the reduction of water reserves and salinity, the type and quality of plants used as food for livestock in pastures will decrease, the area of meadows will be reduced by almost three times. Climate change is one of the major problems of agricultural unusability. As a result of the change of socio-economic and political life in the society, the increase of natural disasters and environmental problems, the possibility of distrust of the future in a certain part of the population in some regions, the weakness of psychological preparation for extreme conditions in life is an urgent problem.

Who lives in the Aral sea areas? We will give you brief information on the ethnopsychological characteristics of the population living in these regions. Many features of the national psychology of the indigenous peoples of the Aral Bay (Islandside) region are explained by the specific nature of the norms and rules of social and cultural life. Karakalpaks and representatives of other nationalities also live in the Aral Bay (Islandside) region. People living in the Aral Bay (Islandside) region have different worldviews, opinions, attitudes to the current environment, and the way they build a family and live. In particular, if we focus on the ethnic

characteristics of the Karakalpak people, we can see their own psychological characteristics from representatives of other nationalities.

The history of the origin of Karakalpaks includes long periods. Karakalpaks are among the powerful peoples. But when they were growing, they were always growing along the river and the Aral Sea. It can be seen from this that the people of Karakalpak were in harmony with nature. He knew many secrets of nature and loved nature. We meet the people in the folk tales and aphorisms that have passed down these qualities orally. Such expressions are always repeated among the people: “Three months of melon, three months of pumpkin, three months of soap, three months of shabagim”, which, in turn, shows the eating habits of the people living in the Orolbuyi region and their adherence to it [10]. So, my melon for three months means that when the melons are ripe, they eat only those types of food, such as “Asqaulaq”, “Melon worm”, “Melon jam”. For three months, Kvavmym has been cooking all these meals with pumpkin and has always said that it is healing. The people of Karakalpak were engaged in fishing and animal husbandry. When I say “souvin-shabag'im”, it means that in the past, different national dishes were prepared from cow's milk curds and fish. Karakalpak women know a variety of fish dishes and emphasize that they are one of the main dishes.

In this kind of scientific psychological approach, it can be concluded that the population is known to have consumed cow's milk and yogurt rather than cow meat, which means that the population has a subjective attitude to natural objects. It is known that they prefer to eat fish than beef, the girls who know 200 different types of dishes from fish also emphasize its fast-digesting medicinal properties. We can see this again in folk proverbs that people who eat fish will be fat and will lose all medicine. We can see that these people are not indifferent to their health and try not to harm their natural resources. Scientific research of this kind tells us that the historical roots of the people's ecological consciousness until recently were positive and subjective. Ethnic psychological features of the Karakalpak people are reflected in the way of life, national culture, art, classical literature, folklore genre, national programs and traditions, but these are a huge scientific resource and they also require specific approaches.

We should pay attention to the ethnopsychological characteristics of the peoples living in the island regions. In the national character of the Karakalpak people, we can clearly see reliability, determination and patience. We witness the national character of the Karakalpak people, first of all, their socio-cultural norms have been formed on the basis of their way of life since ancient times. The preservation of the national identity of the Karakalpak people also consists of stereotypes with ethnic characteristics.

Karakalpaks have well-developed qualities, which are distinguished by hard work, the ability to learn the basics of every job, the ability to learn quickly, a sharp mind, loyalty to their national traditions and pride. The Karakalpak people had a subjective attitude to the nature of the environment in advance, the qualities of courage, responsibility and determination are educationally important, they have a sense of humor, they are active in interpersonal relationships, they have a tendency to think creatively, they have creative imaginations, they are adaptable to any situations, they have developed oral speech. We can witness that many of them are reflected in their national traditions, starting from their way of life.

The administrative-territorial structure of the republic consists of 15 districts and 1 city. These are Amudaryo, Beruniy, Karaozak, Kegeyli, Kungirov, Qonlikol, Moynaq, Nukus,

Takhtakopir, Tortkol, Khojayli, Takhyotosh, Chimboy, Sho'manoy, Ellikkala districts and the city of Nukus [6].

Today, it is known to the general public that the lands of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are rapidly becoming salinized, the population is in a very tragic situation under the influence of the dusty desert air, and various unpleasant environmental phenomena are occurring.

According to the experts, 75 million are released into the atmosphere every year. tons of dust, 4 mln. about tons of harmful substances are being added. Half of these are carbon monoxide, 15% are hydrocarbon emissions, 14% are sulfur dioxide, 9% are nitrogen oxides, 8% are solids, and about 4% are specific acute toxicants [5]. Currently, the sea level is 10 billion. about a ton of salt has been collected, and some of it is spreading around, causing environmental damage.

In November 2020, the World Bank explains that the main reason for the drying up of the Aral Sea is that for nearly 30 years, water resources have been almost completely depleted as a result of the use of various water-intensive crops, including cotton and rice. This has had devastating consequences for the environment and the economy of the Central Asian countries, as well as adversely affecting the well-being and health of millions of people living in this region," researchers said at the time. Every year, Orolqum sand and dust storms cost Uzbekistan and other Central Asian countries 15 million It brings up to 75 million tons of sand, dust, and salt, resulting in soil erosion and air pollution that negatively affects the environment, human health, and well-being [7].

Based on the difficult ecological situation, N.B. Bisaliev states that "it is necessary to pay attention not only to the physical health of every child born in Karakalpakstan, but also to carry out social and medical rehabilitation for their neuro-psychic conditions" [4].

According to a number of authors, demographic indicators have significantly worsened in the Archipelago region over the past 20 years due to the increase in infant and general mortality rates. The main causes of death in this region are diseases of the circulatory system, respiratory and digestive systems [8]. Taking into account that the health of the population is one of the most important resources of the state, it is necessary to constantly monitor the medical-demographic situation and the level of morbidity in this area. As a result of the impact of environmental degradation on the population's health, various diseases, including anemia, cancer, and gastrointestinal diseases, which are widespread among women, are observed. Currently, it is known that the epidemiological indicators of tuberculosis remain one of the serious medical and social problems in the world.

The fact that the inhabitants of the Aral Bay region live in difficult conditions is a feat in itself. However, in the following years, cases of migration to other regions continue. In order to provide the family economically, the cases of going to foreign countries to work as a hired worker have been showing a negative impact on the social and psychological environment of the family. In particular, there are many cases of our young people being deceived by people engaged in "human trafficking" in other countries. Ecological problems always cause economic problems, and the fact that the majority of the population invents life principles and obeys them in a struggle to live in accordance with modern requirements, certainly in turn allows the emergence of social and psychological problems.

Materials and methods

The population, in turn, requires comprehensive psychological training to solve all existing ecological, economic, social and psychological problems. Qualified teachers of various subjects

with comprehensive knowledge of environmental problems and ordinary people became our research respondents. Initially, we conducted questionnaires on the topic "Nature, ecology and me" and " To study the attitude of the population of the Orolbuyi region to the environment " in order to determine the level of environmental awareness among qualified teachers in the educational system . In order to determine the attitude of the inhabitants of the Aral Bay (Islandside) to nature and environmental problems in general, and to distinguish age and gender characteristics in the attitude of the residents of the Aral Bay (Islandside) to the future, the way of living of the inhabitants was observed, and they were interviewed about the existing problems and submitted questionnaires.

Results. In order to achieve the goal of the research, on the topic “Nature, ecology and me” and “To study the attitude of the population of the Aral Bay (Islandside) region to the environment”, experimental materials were obtained regarding the areas and to what extent the attitude of the respondents to nature is manifested. In them, the intensity of the respondents’ subjective attitude to natural objects, their attitude to the nature of the environment was studied .

The results of the survey called “Nature, ecology and me” indicate that our respondents 71.6% noted that the bad nature, the abundance of salt dust in the atmosphere, the deterioration of the water content, these conditions had a negative impact on agriculture. They expressed the opinion that this situation poses a great danger to our society, and the deterioration of the ecological situation will seriously damage not only the economic life, but also the spiritual world of people. In response to this question, 69.2% of the population pointed to tree planting as one of the measures to improve the ecological situation. 15.4% said that harmful waste should be thrown away, and 15.2% said that water should be saved. Seniors pay special attention to environmental cleaning and landscaping, but regrettably noted that after a certain period of time, 80-90% of the work does not produce the expected result. The reason for this is the extreme instability of the ecological situation in the area. Because the land is flooded with salt, the natural composition of the soil is disturbed, and due to the lack of water, one of the important manifestations of ecology, the activities implemented in the area regarding greening do not have the expected effect. He showed people's dissatisfaction with the nature of the environment in his opinion that newly planted trees do not grow green, and old ones continue to wither. Perhaps for this reason, in the results of the questionnaire, it was found that the environmental activity of the respondents was weak (relatively 42%), which means that among our respondents, the indicators of discussing this issue, helping or motivating each other are relatively low, which means the manifestation of a specific, typical environmental consciousness. .

"How is environmental degradation affecting your physical and mental health?" - 56.9% of the respondents chose the answer "to worry about tomorrow". Also, the majority of those who chose such an answer admitted that they are not able to educate people in the spirit of "knowing and understanding nature". But he also left the thoughts that the constant tension causes any work to be ineffective . 24.6% of the respondents reported that they often get angry due to the violation of the existing environmental condition, and 18.4% of the respondents noted that they often experience fatigue and lack of energy.

Observations based on the results of our research revealed that emotionality in the mental state of the population reflects a highly hyperbolized form of environmental consciousness and unpleasant qualities in their behavior.

“Study the attitude of the inhabitants of the Aral Bay (Islandside) region to the environment”, the questionnaire was initially conducted among the inhabitants of Muynoq district, one of the places with severe ecology. This questionnaire was used to determine the satisfaction of the population with the way of life and clarify their cognitive aesthetic, moral and strategic attitudes towards the environment. This questionnaire consists of 50 questions, and we have divided the questions into 5 directions regarding the attitude to the environment. Taking into account the age characteristics of the population, we divided the respondents into 2 groups. Respondents of group 1 are young people aged 15-25, respondents of group 2 are adults aged 25 to 60.

The answers given by the respondents of 2 groups of residents of Aral Bay (Islandside) region, established in Muynoq district, are as follows

	Questionnaire directions	Population attitude (% account)					
		High		Medium		Low	
		Young people aged 15-25	Adults aged 25-60	Young people aged 15-25	Adults aged 25-60	Young people aged 15-25	Adults aged 25-60
1	Determining the feelings of satisfaction with the way of life of the population	18.9	21.8	35.9	37.8	45.2	39.9
2	Cognitive attitude of the population to the environment	36.7	32.4	39.6	46.5	23.7	21.9
3	Aesthetic attitude of the population to the environment	19.6	23.7	34.7	37.3	45.7	38.1
4	attitude of the population to the environment	27.8	34.2	36.7	39.8	35.5	24.2
5	Strategic attitude of the population to the environment	24.9	23.8	34.7	37.8	58.5	38.8

The respondents of the first group of the population, young people aged 15-25 years, had a very low level of satisfaction (39.9%) in the first direction “Determining the feelings of satisfaction with the way of life of the population”, which indicated that living conditions are in a difficult situation due to existing environmental problems and expressed lack of confidence in strategic attitude in future target works. In the questions in the direction of “Cognitive attitude of the population to the environment”, young people have a high (36.7%) desire to learn the causes of environmental problems and how to combat them. During the conversation, they expressed their opinion on maintaining the current state of construction of the "Aral Sea". However, their thoughts are of a general nature. “Can you contribute to the environmental problem?” answered “Yes” to the question. We get information about ecology from social networks and TV shows, and many

people said that they hardly ever read books or magazines. We observed that in their thoughts, in every activity, they are worried about tomorrow, they are worried, and they are often mentally depressed. In these answers, you can see insufficient psychological motivation, lack of experience. That's probably why we see the answer "no use" in the questions in the direction of "Aesthetic attitude of the population to the environment". It can be seen that the first group of respondents formed two different views of their relationship to natural objects. If the first one is characterized by the dominance of subjective perception of natural objects in the environment, we also see the existence of a "subjective attitude" towards them. But the answers in "Aesthetic attitude of the population to the environment" naturally indicate that the environmental tension in the environment has a negative effect on the existing attitude. This, in turn, gives the advantage of "objective perception" to the objects of nature in later periods. In the course of the interview, they mentioned that cognitive relationships with the environment led young people in their interactions with natural objects, they expected cognitive motivation to come from outside rather than from themselves, i.e. supporting and encouraging factors. In the development of any person, there should be a stimulus for personal self-activation, that is, it is desirable for them to first understand and act on their own to deal with various problems. We were concerned about not moving him while having a subjective relationship to the objects of nature in the environment. There was a need to determine the leading motivations for young people, "healthy ecological environment", "greening of education", that is, in relation to them, in interaction with natural objects, which increases social internal activity, forms "collective ecological consciousness".

Respondents of group 2 answered due to the presence of experiences in relation to any environmental phenomena in the environment. However, the high rate in the questions of direction in "Strategic attitude of the population to the environment" is very low (23.8%). The current state of the environment in the population indicates a lack of self-preservation. How the respondents of group 2 perceive the environment, their attitude towards the environmental situation, the level of dissatisfaction with the way of living due to the current environmental situation is high, but despite the high level of dissatisfaction with the current environmental situation, most of them did not want to leave the place where they were born and raised. In this, we can see the primacy of the usual ecological consciousness that has been formed in relation to the environment. Despite the negative perception of the current ecological situation, those who express their desire to leave their place of residence and move to another ecologically more favorable area formed a shortage among the population. This indicates that the population has stereotypes related to the negative ecology of the environment, slow social activity in their future work, and weak motivation to fight violently. Adults should be motivated to take care of their psychological health, self-recovery from psychological crises and the ability to help loved ones with their knowledge in the case of environmental stress. In their relationship to the ecologically difficult conditions in the environment, older adults were able to express daily the issues of solving various existing problems. Other problems related to the ecological situation can be seen in the Aral Bay (Islandside) region. They are many unpleasant situations such as financial problems, birth of unhealthy children, exacerbation of diseases, death of a family member. Studies have shown that chronic environmental stress disrupts the immune and endocrine systems, as well as metabolic processes. All these diseases can lead to diabetes, cancer and other diseases. The ecologically difficult situation describes a situation in which a person's social relations with the environment and normal living conditions are objectively disturbed. The situation begins to be subjectively

perceived as difficult by a person, as a result of which he feels the need for support. True, it is necessary to fight together with the existing problems, for which it is necessary to continuously organize work for ordinary people.

Discussion

Nowadays, in psychology, the characteristics related to the positive characteristics of the personality have come to the fore. Ecopsychological approaches also assume harmony in the interaction of a person with the environment. The above research findings and discussion led us to explore areas with other environmental extremes. Let's say that the country of Japan is one of the areas that often face natural disasters. Japan is located on islands with limited natural resources and space. Japan's various natural forces are tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, that is, Japanese nature is sometimes very cruel to people. But at every step you will see traces of continuous human labor. The Japanese love to observe natural phenomena, there are one hundred and twenty synonyms for the word "rain" in their language. This shows that the Japanese love the nature in their territory, even though they are cruel to people. In Japanese education, starting from the elementary grades, activities to be in harmony with nature are held. In them, Mottainai is a Japanese concept denoting a philosophy and way of life that focuses on caring for the environment and human creation and condemning uneconomic treatment of resources. But it is enough to visit these islands to understand why their inhabitants deify their mother nature. Why don't we teach our young people to love our nature, which was built under the anthropogenic influence, which was beautiful in its time, of course, this is also a sad situation in its place.

It is not difficult to imagine the difficult ecological situation in the Aral Bay (Islandside) region, the above-mentioned examples change the mood of a person at first. It is natural that the mood of the population living in a state of ecological stress often changes, the decrease in mental strength, work ability, the change in the ability to think and the ability to think, increasing distrust in their future work, have an adverse effect on the strategic work of any society. Negative environmental factors weaken human mental capacity, have a negative effect on behavior, psychologists should not be indifferent to these aspects.

In conclusion, it can be stated that it is appropriate to organize a special direction of psychological service among the population in order to eliminate the negative psychological effects of ecological problems on people. Environmental education should be implemented not through separate events and trainings, but on the basis of inculcating ecology in every subject. As one of the priority tasks carried out in education, it is desirable to have a conscious attitude to the environment, not only to make effective decisions from the acquired knowledge, but also to ensure its implementation. It is necessary to preserve anthropomorphism in adolescent students to environmental stress (coping stress), and strengthen epistemological approaches to nature. It is very important to help the population with psychological specialists. Complex psychological approaches are appropriate for studying the development of environmental consciousness of the population, existing ethnic or national stereotypes. He demands to increase the efficiency of using psychological knowledge in ecological education. In order to develop psychological services for the development of environmental awareness, to increase psychological knowledge of environmental situations, a concrete structural system should be created, which will conduct ecopsychological trainings, psychodiagnostic and psychocorrective training step by step. Training should be meaningful and serve as a factor that develops almost stable qualities in the future. According to the content, psychocorrection training should be developed in a general complex that

includes the cognitive sphere, personality characteristics, emotional sphere, behavioral qualities, interpersonal relations, intra-group relations (family, collective), child-parent relations. In addition, individual, group, and formal community programs should be considered separately. In addition, with the help of mass media and social networks, it is necessary to carry out promotion work on the problems of environmental psychology, to develop literature on environmental psychology, educational methodical recommendations. It is necessary to ensure the continuity of psychological diagnosis, psychoprophylaxis and psychocorrection of people living in difficult environmental conditions.

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